

ISic1303

I.Sicily inscription 1303

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἰουλία Γερ[μα]
2. νὰ · ἡ Θεοφιλῆς ἔζη[σεν]
3. ἔτη · ιδ · μῆ(νας) · ια · ἡ(μέρας) · ιΗε · Ἰο[ύλι]
4. [ος·Γ]ερμα[νὸς·γλυκυτά]
5. [τη Θ]υγατ[ρὶ ἐποίη][σεν]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004. Korhonen notes on l.3, while the stone reads HE, his correction of ιε (15 days) may equally be κε (25 days).

Translation (en)

Ioulia Germana who is dear to the gods, lived for 14 years, 11 months and 15 days. Ioulios Germanos built this for his sweetest daughter.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492908

EDCS 39101673

PHI 140795

PHI 316226

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0480 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 100

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